

HyDelta 3

WP4A – Value Chain & System Development - Standardization of hydrogen metrics

D 4,1 – Roadmap to hydrogen metrics standardization

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Executive summary

It is predicted that hydrogen will become increasingly essential in the future energy mix. Currently, the hydrogen value chain uses various metrics like kg, MWh, m³ (n), etc. This study explores the potential of adopting a single unified metric across the hydrogen value chain. Implementing a single unified hydrogen metric would promote uniformity, enhance the transactional framework for businesses, and reduce errors throughout the value chain, thereby supporting the future hydrogen development.

A literature review, substantiated by 10+ interviews with various stakeholders in the hydrogen value chain (from producers to end users), indicates that the current metrics in use—mass-based, volume-based and energy-based—are not ideal. Instead, it is recommended to adopt exclusively energy-based metrics, preferably watt-hour (Wh). This approach offers several advantages, such as reducing confusion, simplifying the integration of green hydrogen certificates into the market, and aligning with other energy markets like the electricity market. However, there are also some pitfalls to consider, including the lack of available direct energy flow metering and the need for further clarity on ways to adopt these metrics, which are addressed in the scenario explanation but also should be addressed in future studies.

It was found that part of the hydrogen chain, specifically mobility, recognizes the benefits but faces practical barriers to switching to (k)Wh. When the practical barriers can't be solved an alternative can therefore be to combine energy-based and mass-based metrics. When a harmonious method of integration can be found, this is also a suitable approach that will enhance the value chain's efficiency and effectiveness.

The study found that, while discussing about calorific values, industry prefers using the Higher Heating Value (HHV) and emphasizes to only use the energy content of the hydrogen molecules present in comparison with the total energy content (i.e., hydrogen share), this is advised to become the common practice. Additionally, the research highlights the importance of hydrogen gas quality and its compliance (in the fuel cell market) with established standards.

To make sure that the hydrogen value chain adopts one metric, support from governmental bodies with the authority to implement changes are essential. Also a norm or standard that can be adopted by different parts of the value chain can help. Time is of the essence here, as the more time it takes, it becomes increasingly difficult to converge to a single metrics. Future studies should focus on the practical implementation of these changes and on standardizing the outcomes of this research.

Samenvatting

Er wordt voorspeld dat waterstof steeds belangrijker zal worden in de toekomstige energiemix. Momenteel gebruikt de waterstofwaardeketen verschillende eenheden zoals kg, MWh, m³ (n), enz. In dit onderzoek wordt het potentieel van de invoering van één enkele eenheid in de hele waterstofwaardeketen onderzocht. De invoering van één waterstofeenheid zal de uniformiteit bevorderen, meer markttransparantie voor bedrijven geven en fouten in de hele waardeketen verminderen. De invoering van een enkele eenheid voor de hele keten zal hiermee de toekomstige waterstofontwikkeling ondersteunen.

Uit literatuuronderzoek, onderbouwd door 10+ interviews met verschillende belanghebbenden in de waterstofwaardeketen (van producenten tot eindgebruikers), blijkt dat de huidige gebruikte meeteenheden - op basis van massa, volume en energie - niet ideaal zijn. In plaats daarvan wordt aanbevolen om uitsluitend energie gebaseerde meeteenheden te gebruiken, bij voorkeur wattuur (Wh). Deze aanpak biedt verschillende voordelen, zoals minder verwarring, eenvoudigere integratie van groene waterstofcertificaten in de markt en uniformiteit met andere energiemarkten zoals de elektriciteitsmarkt. Er zijn echter ook enkele valkuilen waarmee rekening moet worden gehouden, waaronder het gebrek aan meetmethodes om de energiestroom direct te kunnen meten en de behoefte aan duidelijkheid hoe de meeteenheden geïmplementeerd moeten worden. Deze valkuilen worden meegenomen in de uitleg van de scenario's, maar het is aan te bevelen om deze in toekomstige studies verder te onderzoeken.

Er is vastgesteld dat een deel van de waterstofwaardeketen, met name de mobiliteitsmarkt, begrijpt dat het voordelen heeft om over te schakelen naar (k)Wh, maar om verschillende praktische redenen niet bereid is om over te schakelen op energie gebaseerde meeteenheden. Wanneer de praktische bezwaren niet weg genomen kunnen worden, kan het een alternatief zijn om een combinatie te maken van energie en massa gebaseerde eenheden. Als er een eenvoudige integratiemethode kan worden gevonden, is dit ook een geschikte aanpak die de efficiëntie en effectiviteit van de waardeketen zal verbeteren.

Uit het onderzoek blijkt dat, wanneer het over de calorische waardes gaat, de industrie de voorkeur geeft aan het gebruik van de hogere verbrandings waarde (HHV) en dat de energie afrekening plaats vind op het waterstofaandeel van de totale energie-inhoud (de "hydrogen share"). Het wordt daarom aanbevolen om deze specificaties als de standaard te gaan gebruiken. Bovendien benadrukt het onderzoek het belang van de kwaliteit van het waterstofgas en de naleving van de vastgestelde normen (van de brandstofcel markt).

Om ervoor te zorgen dat de waterstofwaardeketen één eenheid gaat gebruiken, is steun van overheidsinstanties met de bevoegdheid om veranderingen door te voeren essentieel. Ook een norm of standaard die door verschillende onderdelen van de waardeketen kan worden overgenomen, kan helpen. Tijd is hier essentieel, hoe langer het duurt, hoe moeilijker het wordt om tot één eenheid te komen. Toekomstige studies moeten zich richten op de praktische implementatie van deze veranderingen en op het standaardiseren van de uitkomsten van dit onderzoek.

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1. Introduction

Countries around the globe are recognizing the potential of hydrogen to reduce the carbon footprint and start their transition towards renewable energy. Currently there are several demonstration projects on hydrogen production that are being developed and performed throughout the whole value chain.

The Netherlands has set ambitious goals to decarbonize the energy system through rapid uptake of green hydrogen in the Dutch energy mix. For example, targets have been set to achieve 500MW of electrolysis capacity for hydrogen generation by 2025 and 3 to 4 GW by 2030. For the European Union, the priority is to produce 10 million tonnes of hydrogen and import an additional 10 million tonnes by 2030.

With these targets, regardless of the units in which it is specified, it can be assumed that hydrogen is set to play a prominent role in the whole de-carbonization and energy transition.

Hydrogen Market – Background & challenges addressed

Hydrogen could become increasingly essential in the future energy mix, offering benefits such as large storage capabilities and efficient transportation. In order for hydrogen to take its potential role, it is crucial to standardize the metrics and metrics used to measure hydrogen across the entire value chain.

Currently, the hydrogen value chain uses various metrics, including tonnes, megawatt hours (MWh), kilowatt hours (kWh), kilograms (kg), cubic meters (m³), and different definitions for the heating value. Given the diverse metrics and the rapid expansion of hydrogen usage, standardization of the metrics and metrics used in the hydrogen industry, will facilitate the upscaling process across the hydrogen value chain, encompassing production, storage, transport, and end use.

Having a single unified hydrogen metric will assist the hydrogen value chain by ensuring uniformity and clarity across all stages, from production to end user. Having an unified metric could improve the transaction framework for businesses and boost technological innovations by providing clear benchmarking. Various studies emphasize that energy consumption can be reduced when customers can easily compare their electricity usage with their gas usage (e.g., hydrogen). Another benefit is that with a single metric, errors in the value chain are less common. This makes the hydrogen value chain more efficient.

Focus of this study – research questions

The aim of this study is to suggest a standardized set of metrics that can be consistently applied throughout the entire hydrogen value chain. HyNetwork Services (HNS) has drafted a first metric-preference list internally to be used during contracting, allocation and balancing with market partners. Along with this, EASEE-Gas has drafted a Common Business Practise (CBP) for the metrics usage recommendations [1].

However, such a first preference list by HNS has not yet been discussed with other market parties throughout the value chain. This work package has the goal to provide a first assessment with entities operating in different parts of the hydrogen supply chain, including producers of hydrogen, technology developers, as well as consumers of hydrogen.

In particular, this work package is set out to research the following questions:

- 1) Which metrics regarding hydrogen, natural gas (NG) and electricity are currently in use throughout the value chain and how do they compare with each other?
- 2) What is/are the most suitable metric/metrics option(s) based on the complex energy transition landscape to become a standard and how should a process of standardization be put into practice?

This research aims to address the aforementioned questions, and this report provides a detailed explanation of the results and the methods used to obtain them.

2. Working Procedure & Current Metrics Overview

In alignment with the objective of the work package, an initial literature study was conducted to compile the current metrics used in the natural gas, electricity, and hydrogen sectors. This literature study facilitated our understanding of the existing metrics in use. Subsequently, the research team conducted interviews with various companies across different segments of the hydrogen value chain. They were asked a series of questions to gather their opinions on the current metrics in use and the possibility of standardization.

The interviews revolved around four topics:

- **Current metrics used in the daily business practices** – This section of the interview focused on the current metrics and metrics used in daily business practices of the company interviewed. The research team explored on why companies adopt specific metrics, how these metrics became mandated and the potential implications of using different metrics.
- **Lower Heating Value (LHV) vs. Higher Heating Value (HHV)** – LHV & HHV are crucial in measuring the energy content of hydrogen as an energy carrier, crucial for assessing its efficiency and performance. The interview specifically addressed which value (LHV or HHV) is currently used within measurements and calculations and the corresponding numerical values applied. Discussions also covered standard temperature and pressure conditions, exploring how changes in these parameters influence LHV and HHV values, essential for accurate energy assessment in hydrogen applications.

Figure 1: Figurative description of Total versus Hydrogen Share [30]

- **Hydrogen Share vs. Total Share** – This is a question related to the energy determination of hydrogen stream. Most hydrogen streams contain impurities. These impurities can either decrease (e.g. N₂, CO₂, etc) or increase (CH₄, C₂H₆, etc) the heating value of the mixtures, see Figure 1. Therefore it has to be agreed upon what part is remunerated and where the costs of optional filtering of the gas are allocated. This holds a close relation with the HyDelta 3.0 work package 1A¹. Additional considerations on this topic can be found in chapter 4.
- **Potential metrics that can be standardized for the whole value chain** – This topic discussed about the potential metrics that could be standardized for the entire value chain. The research team proposed energy based metrics and asked the company to share their views on making this a standard. Additionally, the company's perspective and its openness to adopting the proposed metric were discussed. The concept of standardization procedures was also discussed briefly.

Chapter 3 of this report will discuss the key findings from these interviews, categorized by each segment of the value chain. However, before delving into these findings, it is beneficial to review the different types of metrics currently in use within the value chain and their interrelationships.

Current Metrics Overview

Preliminary research indicated that there currently are different metrics being utilized across the value chain. This section will discuss the diverse metrics and explore their interrelationships with one another. Metrics in which hydrogen is measured can be categorized into 3 types:

- 1) **Energy based** such as Joules (J), Watt-hour (Wh) and British thermal units (Btu) are used to quantify energy content;
- 2) **Mass-based** such as grams (g) or tonnes (ton) are used to quantify the physical mass of hydrogen;
- 3) **Volume-based metrics** such as cubic meters (m³) are utilized to quantify the spatial volume occupied by hydrogen.

In the literature research it was found that the selected metrics and the prefixes of the metrics (i.e. kilo, mega, giga, etc...) depends on the scale of the hydrogen quantification. To create more understanding as to why different metrics and their prefixes are used, a distinction is made between two scales:

- Transportation
- Distribution

An example is for instance the sector where hydrogen is used as a fuel. For transporting ships, typically tonnes is used, while for passenger cars usually kilogram is used.

In order to see the cohesion between the most commonly utilized metrics per scale, two tables are made. These can be used as a reference to recalculate from one metrics to the other. **Please note that the hydrogen is considered to be 100% pure in the metrics conversions.**

¹ Asset Management – Quality Assurance for local hydrogen purity specification (exit & entry)

Gross Calorific value (GCV), standard pressure and temperature are used, so 141.7 MJ/kg, (i.e., at 273.15 K and 101,325 Pa)

Transportation Scale:

On the transportation scale there are 5 metrics identified.

- (Giga)joule: the SI metrics for measuring energy,
- Megawatt-hour: Typically used in the gas and electricity trading markets,
- Tonnes: Typically used when hydrogen is used as bunker fuel,
- Thousand Barrels and Ton oil equivalent: Both typically used in the bunker oil and oil derivatives industry.

In Table 1 the several metrics are given with the factor to recalculate to the other factor.

As an example on how to read the table: 1 ton of hydrogen corresponds to 70.177 Thousand Barrels.

Table 1: Several metrics to quantify hydrogen on a transportation scale.

Unit	GigaJoule (GJ)	Megawatt hour (MWh)	Tonnes (ton)	Thousand Barrels (Mbbl)	Ton oil equivalent (TOE)
GigaJoule (GJ)	1.000	0.278	0.007	0.495	0.024
Megawatt hour (MWh)	3.600	1.000	0.025	1.783	0.086
Tonnes (ton)	141.700	39.361	1.000	70.177	3.384
Thousand Barrels (Mbbl)	2.019	0.561	0.014	1.000	0.048
Ton oil equivalent (TOE)	41.868	11.630	0.295	20.735	1.000

Distribution Scale:

On the distribution scale, the amount of energy per metrics is roughly a factor 1000 lower than with the transportation scale. Table 2 presents commonly used metrics on the distribution side of the value chain.

- (Mega)joule: the SI metrics for energy,
- kilowatt hour: is a typical metrics for measuring household electricity consumption,
- Cubic meter: is a typical metrics for measuring natural gas consumption,
- kilogram (of hydrogen): is a typical metrics used in public refuelling stations,
- Barrel: is typically used in the (US) oil business,
- (kilo) British thermal metrics: is typically used in Heating, Ventilation and Air Conditioning (HVAC) systems.

As an example how to read this table: 1 kilogram of hydrogen is equivalent to 134,3 kilo British thermal metrics.

Table 2: Several metrics to quantify hydrogen on a distribution scale.

Unit	Megajoule (MJ)	kilowatt hour (kWh)	Normal cubic meter (m3(n))	kilogram (kg)	Barrel (bbl)	Kilo British thermal units (kBtu)
Megajoule (MJ)	1	0,278	0,079	0,007	0,495	0,948
kilowatt hour (kWh)	3,6	1	0,283	0,025	1,783	3,412
Normal cubic meter (m3(n))	12,7	3,528	1	0,090	6,290	12,037
kilogram (kg)	141,7	39,361	11,157	1	70,177	134,3
Barrel (bbl)	2,019	0,561	0,159	0,014	1	1,914
kilo British thermal units (kBtu)	1,055	0,293	0,083	0,007	0,523	1

3. Overview of current metrics used in hydrogen value chain

The primary supply of energy for the Dutch energy system in 2022 has been predominantly dominated by natural gas and oil. A report from EBN [2] states that around 36% of the primary energy demand is being supplied by natural gas and around 38% is supplied by oil. Less than 15% of the energy demand is supplied by renewable energy. The estimated plan for 2030 is to increase the share of renewable energy to at least 36% in the Dutch energy mix. Some percentage of this share will be intended to produce hydrogen.

The hydrogen value chain is typically split into 3 fields (see Figure 2):

- 1) Production
- 2) Storage & Distribution
- 3) Utilization

This chapter will discuss the key findings from the interviews we had with different companies over the whole hydrogen value chain, categorized by each segment of the value chain.

Figure 2: Hydrogen Value chain depiction [32]

Hydrogen Production

The first step in the whole value chain is hydrogen production. The production of hydrogen can be classified into 4 significant categories namely [3]:

- 1) Green – Renewable Energy based hydrogen production
- 2) Purple – Nuclear energy based hydrogen production
- 3) Gray – Hydrogen produced from fossil source where CO₂ is vented to the atmosphere
- 4) Blue – Coal gasification and natural gas based production with carbon capture & storage (CCS)

The metrics discussed in this report, can be used to measure hydrogen produced from all the different production methods. According to the European Environment Agency [4], renewable energy sources include wind, solar, aerothermal, geothermal, hydro, ocean energy sources, biomass and the biodegradable fraction of waste. Green hydrogen can for instance be produced from the electrolysis of water with electricity generated by wind or solar produced electricity.

One predominant and common way to produce renewable hydrogen is by electrolysis. Water electrolysis is used to split water into its components of oxygen and hydrogen using electricity. It is a process of splitting water into its component elements, hydrogen and oxygen using an electric current. Positive ions (H⁺) are drawn to the cathode by the electric potential, whereas negative ions (OH⁻) are drawn to the anode [5].

To gain insights into the current metrics used in the hydrogen production industry, the research team interviewed one of the leading Original Equipment Manufacturers (OEMs) of Electrolysers.

The interview with the OEM [6] primarily centred on the metrics they currently utilize for their daily operations, encompassing contracting, remuneration (i.e., commercial billing process in this case), and production. Following a thorough understanding of their current metrics, the discussion shifted towards exploring the feasibility of standardizing metrics across the entire value chain and identifying which metrics would be most appropriate for comprehensive adoption. Some key findings from the interviews are discussed below.

Key findings:

- Current metrics used – The current metrics used for electrolyser is **kg/hour or tons/day**, but is always displayed as **mass per time**.
- On a daily basis, the heating value within the company is based on the higher heating value (HHV) and the efficiency is denoted as kWh/kg. Typical energy consumption of an electrolyser is around 50-55 kWh/kg, with an HHV content of 39,2 kWh/kg and an LHV energy content of 33,3 kWh/kg.
- The current remuneration and billings are done **with hydrogen share**.
- The interview revealed that **energy-based metrics** should serve as the foundation for the standardization of metrics across the hydrogen value chain.
- Additionally, it was concluded that if standardization of metrics is to be achieved, a designated regulatory body should take the lead in coordinating efforts and ensuring alignment within the industry.

Hydrogen transport

The next step in the hydrogen value chain is the transportation of the "produced" hydrogen. Due to the diverse production methods and potential end uses, the transportation of hydrogen varies significantly for each scenario. Hydrogen can be transported in various forms, either as pure hydrogen or in the form of other energy carriers such as ammonia (NH₃) and methanol (MeOH). Hydrogen can also be cooled to create liquid hydrogen (LH₂). The form in which hydrogen is transported also depends on the requirements and specifications of the end user. For the purposes of this research, we are assuming that hydrogen will be transported in gaseous form, rather than liquified or in form of a hydrogen carrier(s).

There are various ways to transport hydrogen from one location to another, with the choice of method largely dependent on the distance involved. Some common transportation methods include:

- **Pipeline transportation:** Preferred for medium/long-distance transport.
- **Local transportation by tube trailers and bottles/racks:** Used for shorter, local distances and relatively low quantities.
- **Overseas transportation;** typically done when transport distances are very long and in form of a hydrogen carrier or in the liquid phase.

Pipeline transportation is generally favored for moving hydrogen over longer distances, whereas tube trailers and bottles/racks are typically employed for local or shorter-distance transport needs with lower quantity of hydrogen transport.

To gain insights into the current metrics used in the hydrogen production industry, the research team interviewed some of the Distribution System Operators (DSOs) of the Netherlands.

The interviews [7] primarily focused on the metrics they currently utilize for their daily operations, encompassing contracting, transporting, remuneration and gas measurement. Following a thorough understanding of their current metrics, the discussion shifted towards assessing how changes in metrics would impact gas meters and billing for the general population. This led to an exploration of the feasibility of standardizing metrics across the entire value chain and identifying the most appropriate metrics for comprehensive adoption. Some key findings from the interviews are discussed below

Key Findings:

- Current Metrics used - The current metrics for measuring hydrogen in pipelines are in **Normal cubic meters (Nm³)**, (i.e., volume-based metrics)
- Currently with DSOs, the current metrics used for buying of hydrogen via tube trailers to carry out pilot projects are in **kilograms (mass based)** and the remuneration is via m³ (volume based)
- Although volume-based metrics are currently used in pipeline transportation, Distribution System Operators (DSOs) are open to transitioning to energy-based metrics (e.g., Watt-hours (Wh) or Joules (J)).
- Transitioning to energy-based metrics presents additional challenges for DSOs, such as:
 - Adjusting or replacing gas meters accordingly (i.e., replacing the current "Bellows-type meters" to "Ultrasonic meters").
 - Addressing public perception, especially if the end use is for heating buildings (more details in subsequent chapters).

- Changes and mandates has to be made in the entire smart metering gas data stream. (the EDSN portal, where the data generated and send by the smart meters, is collected and shared to the grid operators and energy suppliers).
- Managing the complexities and difficulties associated with implementing changes to the entire system.

Hydrogen Utilization

The last step in the whole hydrogen value chain is the “Utilization and end users”. Hydrogen, as a versatile and clean energy carrier, is gaining significant attention for its potential to revolutionize various sectors through end-user utilization. Hydrogen has a long history of being utilized in a wide variety of industries, and the majority of hydrogen today is used in fields like ammonia production, methanol production and oil refining. However, with the new production methods and the need to reduce carbon emissions, hydrogen is increasingly being used outside-the-box ways to produce both old and new products [8]. Few sectors in which hydrogen could act as a game-changer are listed below. **Fout! Verwijzingsbron niet gevonden.** represents an example of possible end uses.

1) Transportation | Mobility Sector:

In the transportation sector, hydrogen is primarily utilized through fuel cells, offering a clean and efficient alternative to fossil fuelled internal combustion engines (ICE’s). Fuel Cell Electric Vehicle (FCEV) is a type of vehicle that uses compressed hydrogen gas as fuel to generate electric power via a fuel cell. The fuel cell transforms the hydrogen into electricity to power an electric engine [9]. FCEVs offer a cheaper, quieter and more efficient mobility option. This technology is employed in various vehicle types, including: cars [10], buses and trucks [11], rail transport [12] and maritime & aviation.

2) Fuel & Feedstock for Industry:

Multiple uses for industry can be grouped into two categories:

- a. Hydrogen as a feedstock
- b. Hydrogen as fuel for industry

Hydrogen is primarily used as a component or as a feedstock in ammonia production, oil refining (hydrothermal cracking) and methanol production, these three processes currently make up the majority of hydrogen utilisation [8].

3) Built Environment – Residential & Commercial heating

Hydrogen usage in built environment represents a transformative approach in achieving sustainability and energy efficiency in residential, commercial and urban infrastructure. In residential and commercial settings, hydrogen can be utilized for heating, power generation, and as a backup energy source, reducing reliance on fossil fuels and lowering greenhouse gas emissions. Hydrogen can be integrated into the built environments in the following ways:

- a. Hydrogen Boilers or Hydrogen Blended with NG
- b. Fuel Cells
- c. Combined Heat and Power System

The Dutch town of Lochem is the first town in the world where twelve existing houses are heated using hydrogen transported over the repurposed natural gas grid. Alliander, a Dutch DSO holding for electricity and natural gas is leading this project to investigate and demonstrate that heating homes with hydrogen through the existing natural gas grid is a good alternative for electrical heating. The realisation of the hydrogen distribution network in Lochem and its commissioning took place in 2022. This pilot project will run for three years [13].

Figure 3: An example of what a hydrogen cycle could look like, including possible end uses [8]

The research team aimed to understand the current metrics used in the hydrogen industry by interviewing key players across different end users. However, due to external constraints, the team managed to conduct interviews with only a select few members of the end user value chain [14]. The team managed to hold interviews with key players from re-fuelling station and build environment (i.e., Lochem project).

The interviews with end users [15] primarily focused on metrics they currently utilize for their daily operations, encompassing contracting, transporting and remuneration. Following a thorough understanding of their current metrics, the discussion shifted towards exploring the feasibility of standardizing metrics across the entire value chain and identifying which metrics would be most appropriate for comprehensive adoption. Some key findings from the interviews are discussed below.

Key Findings:

- For the Lochem project, the contractor measures the amount of hydrogen and then converts it on an energy basis to the matching volume of natural gas (in m³). This conversion allows for the reuse of pricing and grid tariffs applicable for the natural gas system. Also, in this way, the residents can compare their hydrogen bill with the familiar natural gas bills.
- At refuelling stations, hydrogen is currently sold using mass-based metrics (i.e., kilograms). This preference for kilograms is due to industrial & local environmental standards and the straightforward billing process for customers.

- Reconciliation is a settlement method used to address the differences between actual and estimated measurements of gas allocated to various supply points. The Dutch TSO (GTS) employs energy-based metrics, to prepare their reconciliation invoices.
- As mentioned in Sections 2.3, the Distribution System Operator (DSO) of the Netherlands, Alliander, who is leading the Lochem Project, is open to transitioning from volume-based metrics to energy-based metrics. However, this change in metrics heavily depends on public opinion, which could play a crucial role in the implementation process along with the standardization of the unit.
- Some end users, such as refuelling stations, are not open to changing their current mass-based metrics to energy-based metrics due to several reasons:
 - Anticipated difficulties in adapting and implementing the new metrics
 - Current business processes run smoothly with kilograms, and industries are accustomed to this system
 - Creating new guidelines is a time-consuming process, and the hydrogen market will be highly developed by then
 - Some environmental and local permits specify hydrogen measurements in kilograms or tonnes [16]

Metering/Measurement companies

As the hydrogen infrastructure expands, accurate metering and measurement systems are essential for maintaining safety, optimizing flow, and ensuring fair billing and accountability. Accurate measurement of gas quality is crucial for managing storage facilities and integrating with renewable energy sources [17].

To know more about the metering/measuring companies perspective of hydrogen metrics, the research team interviewed two measuring companies; one located in the Netherlands, and one in United Kingdom.

The interview [18] primarily focused on metrics they currently utilize for their daily operations. Following a thorough understanding of their current metrics, the discussion shifted towards exploring the feasibility of standardizing metrics across the entire value chain and identifying which metrics would be most appropriate for comprehensive adoption. Some key findings from the interviews are discussed below.

Key Findings:

- Currently, buying of hydrogen for testing purposes is done on a volume based metrics (i.e., Litres), because this type of gas is usually shipped in cylinders.
- Usually blend ratios are in volume based metrics.
- Metering companies agree that billing of hydrogen should be energy based metrics. Currently, not a lot of mass based metrics are used in UK.
- UK based companies [19] would like to see one standard as a common basis and speak the same language with EU, and energy based metrics would be agreed upon.

Reflection

The previous sections of the report focused on the key finding of the 10+ interviews that were conducted with key stakeholders from the entire value chain. The interviews focused on key questions mentioned in Chapter 2 - Working Procedure & Current Metrics Overview.

Figure 4: Key findings/results based on the interviews. Note that the interviewees from the Hydrogen Utilisation side included mobility-based end users (i.e., hydrogen refuelling stations).

Figure 4 presents the key findings in a value chain format. From all the interviews, it was found that different segments of the hydrogen value chain use varying metrics of measurement. For instance:

- **Hydrogen producers** currently use mass-based metrics such as kilograms (kg) or tonnes.
- **Hydrogen distributors (TSO/DSO)** continue to use volume-based metrics (m³) inherited from the natural gas system, but the bill is in energy content based on m³ (corrected for energy content)
- **Hydrogen utilization** metrics vary depending on the application: built environments use volume-based metrics (m³), while other sectors use mass based metrics.

Lower Heating Value (LHV) or the Higher Heating Value (HHV)

LHV is defined as the amount of heat released by a specific quantity of a combustible component (at 25°C) once it is completely combusted, the temperature of the combustion products cooled down to 25°C and with the water produced remaining as a vapor. Therefore, it does not take into account the latent heat of vaporisation of water in the combustion products [20].

HHV is defined as the amount of heat released by a specified quantity (initially at a temperature of 25°C) once it is combusted and the products have returned to a temperature of 25°C, which takes into account the latent heat of vaporisation of water in the combustion products. It is also known as the gross calorific value (GHV) or gross value. [21]

From the interviews, it was found that there were logical reasons for using the HHV as a standard in hydrogen assessments.

- As there is a tendency for processes to become more efficient, using latent heat is utilized more during (future) processes.

- In most types of fuel cell, hydrogen completely reacts with oxygen and temperatures are typically well below 100 degrees, including the latent heat in the process.
- Using the HHV solves the problem of having a “indicated” efficiency above 100%. If the HHV is used the efficiency never exceeds 100%, making comparisons easier.
- Currently, the hydrogen producers base their heating value on the higher heating value, which is now industry wide accepted. In the interview with hydrogen producers [6] it was mentioned that the EU use a value of of 39 kWh/kg in their tenders, which is based on the 100% efficiency when using the HHV. A typical efficiency that is required for electrolyzers is 52kWh per kg hydrogen produced, leading to a required overall efficiency of 75% for electrolyzers.

Hydrogen share vs Total Share

The recommendation of this research is to use the hydrogen share for remuneration of the delivered hydrogen. The total share includes contaminants which can increase or decrease the heating value (methane will increase the heating value, where e.g. nitrogen will decrease the heating value). However even if the heating value is increased, it remains an contaminant. For hydrogen combustion processes this might not be that relevant, however if we look at the predicted usage of hydrogen (feedstock and fuel cells) any contaminants are unwanted and need to be removed before utilization. It is therefore recommended that the hydrogen share is used, to encourage specifically blue hydrogen producers to deliver the cleanest hydrogen (economically) possible and avoid the presence of “valueless” hydrocarbons.

Potential Standardization

Within the hydrogen value chain various metrics are being used. Mass or Volume based metrics are predominately used:

- Producers and some end users using **mass based metrics like kg or tonnes.**
- Transportation, measurement companies and some end users using **volume based metrics like m³ (n) or litres, but also recalculated to energy.**

One of the objectives of this study was to determine if a unified metric can be identified and adopted across the entire hydrogen value chain. It was found that there was a common thread in most (not all) of the interviews.

Although mass and volume-based metrics are predominantly used in the hydrogen industry today, insights from the interviews revealed that these metrics are not ideal for hydrogen operations. Industry experts expressed concerns about the limitations of mass and volume measurements in capturing the full energy potential and efficiency of hydrogen.

On the other hand, most of the industrial experts (not all) agree that shifting towards energy based metrics will have its merits and benefits to their businesses and the hydrogen economy. They feel that using energy-based metrics would provide a more accurate and useful standard for the entire value chain. Especially as there is a tendency towards electrification and the close relation renewable hydrogen has with electricity.

The research team also feels that this shift towards energy based metrics would help to align measurements with the energy output and facilitate better integration with existing energy systems, ultimately supporting boosting of an effective hydrogen economy.

Some industrial experts that the research team interviewed, had their concerns about transitioning from the existing methods to entirely new energy-based metrics. They highlighted potential challenges

such as the complexity of adapting current systems, and the time required to develop and implement new guidelines.

Additionally, there were apprehensions about the public's acceptance of the new metrics and the potential disruption to established business processes that currently operate smoothly with mass and volume-based measurements.

4. Scenarios towards a common hydrogen metrics

In order to create a common industry alignment across the hydrogen supply chain (for example across the parties who would become users of a hydrogen network), there can be two main scenarios to create uniformity regarding metrics of measurement of hydrogen flow:

- **Scenario 1:** A single metric across the entire value chain (e.g., energy-based).
- **Scenario 2:** Co-existence of mass based & energy based metrics across the value chain.

In the following section, we will discuss the implications of each scenario within the context of the hydrogen supply chain i.e., considering the same supply chain as we discussed in the previous section.

Scenario 1: Energy based metrics across the entire value chain

One of the potential scenarios to create alignment across the hydrogen supply chain is to have the whole supply chain adopt an **energy-based hydrogen metering metrics e.g., MWh**. The choice of energy as being the basis metrics is driven by the international market:

- Currently the markets for different energy carriers (e.g., electricity, oil, natural gas) utilise energy metrics as basis: MWh (Megawatt-hour), Mboe (millions of barrels of oil equivalent), MMBtu (millions of British Thermal Metrics), etc.

As such, choosing an energy metrics could be a logical choice to align a (future) hydrogen trading market with those of other energy carriers.

Advantages of having energy based metrics:

- 1) One of the main advantages of adopting an energy-based metrics across the whole hydrogen supply chain is that the metrics would be harmonised i.e., there would be no confusion when discussing hydrogen trade. This can be of particular interest when discussing hydrogen-based contracts. Even for contracts that don't necessarily imply the purchase of hydrogen molecules (as would be the case when discussing for connection contracts to a hydrogen network), there can be a higher level of transparency to all parties involved in the discussion understand and utilise energy-based flows as basis.
- 2) The adoption of energy based as the primary metrics for hydrogen metering would facilitate the integration of green hydrogen certificates into the market. These certificates, crucial under regulations like the EU's Renewable Energy Directive (RED), set targets for low-carbon hydrogen consumption in various industries, measured in energy metrics (e.g., MWh). This framework would require industrial users to use hydrogen and acquire green hydrogen certificates. These certificates are expected to be issued in energy terms (e.g., MWh of hydrogen), akin to markets for green electricity and gas, ensuring smooth operation. This approach would lead to a smooth operation on how hydrogen consumers demonstrate their use and purchase of green hydrogen certificates, enhancing transparency and accountability.

- 3) Another main advantage of the adoption of a common energy-based flow metrics is that, since this is the common type of metrics used in other energy markets including the natural gas market, a lot of the rules and regulations that pertain energy flows could be adopted in an easier manner. As a result, having hydrogen measured in energy flow could lead to an acceleration of the development of rules and regulations pertaining to a hydrogen market, where the current market rules are currently non existing, not all-encompassing, or in development.

Pitfalls to be careful about:

- 1) One of the main implications of this scenario is that the energy flow of hydrogen (e.g., MWh-H₂/h or simply MW) is a secondary measurement derived from either mass flow metering or volumetric flow metering. This is because at least in the current state of the hydrogen supply chain, mass flow and volume flow are the main forms of hydrogen flow metering. There are no available energy flow meters for hydrogen that directly measure energy content. All currently available meters are based on measuring either volume or mass flows. The main consequence of this implication is that, in case an energy-based metrics is adopted by the whole supply chain, there would have to be an overarching standard that defines the conversion rate between energy and mass/volume. Examples of such a standard could include a ministerial ruling, a standard (either national or international) or a document adopted by an industry association.
- 2) Another question requiring clarification is whether adoption of these metrics should occur solely among participants involved in energy flows (such as hydrogen producers, transporters, and distributors) or if technology developers, such as electrolyser and sensor manufacturers, should also adopt these metrics.

As example, some of the supply chain participants interviewed in this project include electrolyser developers, who often mainly sell equipment instead of the hydrogen molecules. Electrolyser equipment is rated, according to the ISO 22734 (a standard that defines hydrogen generators using water electrolysis), to express their maximum hydrogen production rate in metrics of either mass or volume per metrics time. Since compliance with the ISO 22734 is mandatory for electrolyser systems to be sold in the market (i.e., to obtain CE certification), adding energy flow metrics would require either an amendment of the standard, or compliance with another reference document. Moreover, electrolysers also need to show (also as part of the ISO 22734) a rated power in kW or MW while energy flow per metrics time can also have metrics of power (e.g., MWh/h or simply MW). This situation often leads to confusion within the supply chain. The rated power of an electrolyser (e.g., MW) has been often wrongly interpreted as being the maximum hydrogen output (in energy metrics), a situation that has led to overestimations of the maximum hydrogen throughput of an electrolyser. In summary, it is important to define which market participants are mandated to use energy metrics when discussing hydrogen and which participants can keep the metrics that lead to adherence with e.g., the standards and reference documents of their respective industries.

- 3) A final point to pay attention to is to create alignment along the hydrogen purity standards along the supply chain, in particular related to how energy content of hydrogen is counted i.e., whether hydrogen energy flow will also count the energy content of impurities or not.

According to the ISO 14687 (a standard that establishes several hydrogen purities for end uses involving fuel cells as well as heat), different hydrogen grades have a varying limit of hydrocarbon

content, which would contribute to the energy content of a hydrogen flow when used in heating applications. This is also explained in chapter 2 where the total share vs hydrogen share is addressed. Table 3 shows a summary of the gaseous hydrogen grades, as well as their corresponding maximum level of (hydrocarbon) impurities, specified in 1) the ISO 14687, 2) the indicative quality conditions of the DNV/KIWA study supported by the Dutch Ministry of Economic Affairs and Climate Policy [22], and 3) the CEN/TS 17977:2023 standard [23].

Table 3. Different hydrogen quality grades and corresponding maximum allowable hydrocarbon contents, according different standards.

Hydrogen Quality Type and Grade according to the ISO 14687	Example applications	Hydrogen fuel index (minimum mole fraction)	Maximum total impurities content [ppm]	Maximum hydrocarbon content [ppm]
Type I Grade A	Gaseous hydrogen for small-scale combustion appliances (e.g., residential)	98%	20.000	100
Type I Grade B	Gaseous hydrogen for industrial fuel (e.g., power generation)	99,9%	1.000	Not specified (Non-condensing hydrocarbons at all ambient conditions)
Type I Grade C	Gaseous hydrogen for aircrafts and ground vehicle operations	99,995%	50	Not specified
Type I Grade D	Gaseous hydrogen for PEM fuel cells in road vehicles	99,97%	300	102 (including methane and longer-chain hydrocarbons)
Type I Grade E Category 3	Gaseous hydrogen for stationary PEM fuel cells	99,9%	1.000	102 (including methane and longer-chain hydrocarbons)
Indicative quality specification for Hydrogen Network Netherlands (HNS)	Industrial specification in the Netherlands including refining (hydrocracking)	99,5%	5.000	5.000 (total sum of hydrocarbons including methane as long as the hydrocarbon dewpoint is -2°C)
CEN/TS 17977 Technical specification. Gas infrastructure – Quality of gas – Hydrogen used in rededicated gas systems	Hydrogen transport in rededicated gas systems, taking into account the condition of existing piping with possible presence of liquid and solid deposits	98%	20.000 (the content and composition shall satisfy a Wobbe Index range of 42,0-46,0 MJ/m ³ 15°C/15°C)	Hydrocarbon dewpoint is specified at -2°C at pressures between 1 and 70 bar)

	influencing the hydrogen quality			
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From Table 3 it can be seen that different hydrogen quality grades specified in the ISO 14687 have a varying degree of maximum allowable impurity content, although most quality grades tend to converge in the same maximum for hydrocarbon content: 100 ppm. Conversely, hydrogen Type I Grade B, which according to the ISO 14687 would be hydrogen used in industrial heating and power applications, does not have a maximum limit of hydrocarbons. The main parameter specifying the total impurities content of Hydrogen Type I Grade B is 1.000 ppm, which is ten times higher than the limit of most of the other grades except Type I Grade C (aircraft and ground vehicles operation). Note that the ISO 14687 does not contain an extensive list of hydrogen quality types used in industry; notable types missing include the typical hydrogen quality for hydrocracking in refineries (~99,5%) or hydrogen for ultra-pure applications including laboratory work (~99,999%). Most of the ISO 14697 hydrogen purity grades are currently used as reference for some hydrogen supply chain actors including electrolyser manufacturers, hydrogen refuelling stations, stationary fuel cells, etc.

The indicative standard recommended by DNV and KIWA leads to a minimum hydrogen concentration of 99,5%. According to the study, this specification was found to be the optimum based on a minimization of the total purification costs for the whole hydrogen supply chain taken into account the usage of repurposed natural gas pipelines, and most likely considering that refineries are expected to be some of the largest users of hydrogen. As was mentioned before, hydrocracking requires hydrogen purities of around 99,5%, which is currently missing as a Grade in the ISO 14687. The DNV/KIWA proposal is currently being discussed in Europe and therefore not adopted yet in Dutch law.

Furthermore, the CEN/TS (TS means “Technical Specification”) 17977 sets a hydrogen quality for transporting it in reused natural gas pipelines. While the hydrocarbon content of both the DNV/KIWA and the CEN/TS 17977 is similar, the CEN/TS 17977 sets a lower minimum hydrogen quality of 98%.

As such, while the ISO 14687 is being used by (some) end users, both the indicative quality specification by DNV/KIWA and the CEN/TS 17977 are expected to involve the hydrogen (pipeline) transport industry. One of the main consequences of the difference between the different (proposed) standards (ISO 14687, DNV/KIWA, and CEN/TS 17977) is that there could be differences in the hydrocarbon content. This can lead to that the method of counting the energy content of hydrogen being potentially different (for example lower concentrations of hydrocarbons might require different and more expensive detection equipment than higher concentrations). This is relevant mainly because hydrocarbons also contain energy, so the question whether the hydrocarbon content should be counted or not may depend on the standard that each supply chain participant uses.

That being said, it is important to separate the production of hydrogen and the transport of hydrogen. Producers of hydrogen might deliver hydrogen with a high grade to a grid. Grid operators (especially DSOs) have no means to keep the hydrogen to a certain purity level. So, the given specification is a minimum. The hydrogen feed can be influenced during transport through the grid (including components such as water, sand, and other types of pollutants to the hydrogen), especially in repurposed infrastructure that involve the reuse of natural gas pipelines where trace components might be desorbed from materials such as H-PVC and onto the hydrogen grid (as was found in previous HyDelta research). There could be differences in the types and amounts of pollutants that can be found in distribution and transmission networks due to potential differences in operations (e.g., the use of pigging) or in grid configurations (e.g., mazed vs non-mazed networks).

As mentioned in Chapter 2, it is advised to use the hydrogen share for all economic activities (e.g., remuneration) purposes. Moreover, alignment would need to be sought on the minimum guaranteed quality (and energy content) of the hydrogen in the European pipeline systems between hydrogen producers, transporters, and consumers.

Scenario 2: Co-existence of multiple flow metrics across the value chain e.g., mass-based and energy-based flows

Another potential scenario is the co-existence of multiple hydrogen flow metrics across the value chain. From the interviews carried out as well as from past experience it is clear that the supply chain is more in favour of the adoption of energy-based and mass-based flow metrics instead of volume-based flow metrics.

Textbox #1: impact of different standards of reference temperature and pressure conditions and impact of adopting volume-based flow metrics

From the interviews conducted in the hydrogen supply chain, it became clear that volume-based flow metrics are the least popular of the options. This may come as a surprise considering that volume-based flow metering is significantly cheaper than mass-based flow metering.

One of the main advantages of volume-based metrics is that this is a primary metric i.e., it can be measured directly by a device at a lower cost than the other alternatives. As such, there would not be any conversion factor needed from volume to e.g., energy. The main limitation of using volume-based metrics (for example m³/h (n)) is that implementation of such a metric as a standard metric across all the market participations, could become cumbersome. As an example, we can study the case of the definition of a “m³ (n)” (normal cubic meter).

The definition of m³ (n) is based on a set of reference conditions of temperature and pressure i.e., the so-called Normal Temperature and Pressure (NTP). That being said, there is no international consensus on what these reference NTP conditions actually are:

Reference “Normal” temperature [K]	Reference “Normal” pressure [Pa]	Hydrogen density at the reference “Normal” conditions [kg/m ³ (n)]	Deviation with respect to “Normal” conditions: 273,15 K and 101.325 Pa	Organisation that uses these reference conditions
273,15	101.325	0,0892	0%	EASEE [26] MR Gaskwaliteit [27]
273,15	100.000	0,0881	-1%	IUPAC [28]
288,15	101.325	0,0846	-5%	ISO 13443
288,71	101.325	0,0844	-5%	API [29]
294,15	101.325	0,0828	-7%	NIST [30]

As a result, adopting volume-based metrics internationally without a consensus on what values should be used on NTP, could lead to a deviation in the calculations of up to 7% simply by the varying definitions of NTP by standardisation institutions and key organisations involved in the hydrogen supply chain. In contrast, the definition of mass (e.g., kg or metric tonnes) and energy (e.g., MWh) is (more) homogeneous at an international level. The main hurdle with energy-based flow metrics is that a definition is needed whether the energy metrics are based on the Lower Heating Value/Net Caloric Value (LHV or NCV) or the Higher Heating Value/Gross Caloric Value (HHV/GCV) of hydrogen.

It is important to also mention that the definitions of energy content (e.g., HHV/GCV) are not homogeneous and sometimes differ from the definitions of the reference conditions for volume-based metrics. In particular, the Dutch MR Gaskwaliteit (which determines the reference conditions for natural gas energy and volume metrics) establishes that, while the volume (m³ (n)) of natural gas should be established as 273,15 K, the energy content (HHV/GCV) of natural gas should be established at 298,15 K; this is also the case in the Common Business Practices by EASEE. The difference in energy content is not so significant but still relevant to mention that the HHV/GCV calculated with both reference temperatures are not exactly the same:

HHV/GCV of hydrogen at 273,15 K	HHV/GCV of hydrogen at 298,15 K	Difference
39,4	39,3	0,24%

Another potential advantage of the co-existence of multiple metrics is that the agreements related to hydrogen purchase, in particular where energy flows and hydrogen quality are involved, can be done on a bilateral basis instead of having to reach an industry-wide consensus on the metrics of measurement to be used. This could lead to faster contracting agreements, although the disadvantage is that the same party could be facing, for example, contract negotiations with different parties based on different flow metrics, leading to potential confusion and longer contract negotiations than in the case the same metrics would be adopted.

Textbox #2: use of different metrics and impact of different hydrogen qualities on price

The use of different hydrogen flow metrics could result in easier discussions in the hydrogen supply chain, with respect to the adoption of a common (energy-based) metric, pertaining to the different costs of different hydrogen purities. For example, the same unit of energy (e.g., 1 MWh) of hydrogen Grade A (98%) and hydrogen Grade C (99,995%) would yield a similar amount of energy, yet the cost of purifying hydrogen from Grade A to Grade C could be significantly higher, leading to a potential situation where the seller of Grade C hydrogen can potentially ask for a higher price than the seller of Grade A hydrogen.

Having a mass-based metric, for example, can lead to a customer getting full transparency on the amount of hydrogen they are receiving, which is of particular importance in electrolyzers since their rated output (e.g., kg/h) is the amount of actual hydrogen produced instead of the amount of hydrogen contained in a mixture with a particular energy content. That being said, a potential way forward is to determine hydrogen prices according to different purities as is done with technical gases, like for example helium, that respond to different situations such as availability, purity, but also cost of production.

One further consequence of having a co-existence of different hydrogen flow metrics, is that no industry-wide agreements need to be reached before a (regulated) hydrogen market is established, since there would not be a departure from the state of the art. While this could be seen as a positive in terms of the pathway to development of a hydrogen market, it could also present a disadvantage to some market participants, especially related to the topic of green hydrogen certification as was discussed above. Having different metrics of flow measurement could lead to confusion regarding green hydrogen certificate, considering that they are expected to be issued in metrics of energy (as is done with green electricity and green gas certificates). As example, a customer who buys green hydrogen certificates (measured in MWh) but buys the actual hydrogen molecule from a vendor where the contract is in volume metrics (measured in e.g., m³/h (n)), would have a difficult time correlating the volume flow with the energy flow without an industry-adopted conversion factor from volume to energy flows.

Way forward & Follow up

The previous section of the report (i.e., Section 4) briefly presented the results and the key findings that were obtained from this research. In the section, our focus now shifts towards how best to harness these findings to reach a more effective way forward. It is crucial to strategically work on these insights, and to create actionable use cases. We'll discuss on how to integrate our findings within the current way of working and some key factors that need attention.

- 1) To mandate the scenarios mentioned, it requires the involvement of official and influential organizations empowered to implement such rules. This mandate must originate from recognized bodies capable of creating standards, such as the **EU, CEN/NEN organizations, or national institutes dedicated to standardization**. Collaboration with industry and research institutes will be essential to develop these standards taking this research as a basis to build upon.
- 2) The HyDelta program engages key stakeholders in the Netherlands, including influential entities like Netbeheer Nederland (a collaboration of Dutch TSO & DSOs). Their participation not only enhances the program's credibility but also provides crucial leverage for implementing mandated changes. Collaborative support from these partners can serve as a catalyst, bolstering efforts to establish these scenarios as mandatory standards.
- 3) European Association for the Streamlining of Energy Exchange – gas (**EASEE-gas**) is an organization comprised of around 80 companies active in the EU gas market, who facilitate the transition to a sustainable and integrated energy system in Europe. EASEE Gas recently introduced a Common Business Practice (CBP) outlining recommended metrics for hydrogen market processes, aligning closely with the findings of this research. Leveraging this alignment, EASEE Gas could advocate more vigorously for standardizing energy-based metrics among all future members of hydrogen transport organizations. This strategic alignment could strengthen the case for widespread adoption and streamline operational practices across the industry.
- 4) During the transition period towards a unified metric system, multiple metrics can continue to be used as they are currently employed. To facilitate the smooth operation of this multi-metrics system, conversion factors highlighted in Chapter 2 can aid in transitioning between different metrics. However, this approach may also present pitfalls, which will be addressed in the following paragraph.

Additionally some pitfalls that need to be given attention to:

- 1) The conversion rate (i.e., from mass to energy or volume to energy), would have to be defined in a particular set of reference conditions of parameters such as temperature and pressure. As an example, the standard EN 16726 (a standard that defines the gas quality in gas infrastructure in Europe) defines so-called 'standard' reference conditions i.e., at 15°C and 1,01325 bar. That being said, other standards and documents that define other sets of reference conditions (sometimes called 'normal' reference conditions i.e., 0°C and 1 bar, etc.). As a result, attention needs to be paid that all the supply chain participants adhere to a particular set of reference conditions in order for everyone to use the exact same conversion factor from primary flow measurement output (i.e., mass or volume flow) to energy flow.

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